

METHODS OF TEACHING VOLLEYBALL IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *In college volleyball education, the traditional teaching method emphasizes too much on the transmission of knowledge and insufficient cultivation of students' independent learning ability, which leads to the lack of students' interest in learning and makes college volleyball teaching ineffective. In order to improve the quality of college volleyball education, the use of independent learning methods in teaching can make students independently analyses, think and summarize volleyball knowledge, thus improving students' independent learning ability.*

Keywords: *teaching volleyball; educational institutions; learning methods; volleyball instruction.*

The development of current volleyball emphasizes more on three-D attacks. In such an improvement trend, the educating of volleyball blocking off technological know-how is very important, and it is very vital to analyze the educating hyperlinks and education strategies pertinently.[1] When educating volleyball in physical training lessons, it is beneficial to have a range of activities, educating models, and patterns in the toolbox to help ensure college students make incredible progress. Volleyball training can be delivered in a vary of methods depending upon the age, team size, sources available, and your degree of expertise of the game. Due to the complexity of volleyball, most PE instructions will have a considerable disparity of abilities. From students who have been taking part in for a membership for years to these who might also have never played in their lives. Thus, you will need a vary of things to do and duties in order that all students are optimally challenged.[2] From individual skill activities, cooperative duties and rallies, to ability specific activities. It may also additionally be fine with older college students to utilize the trip in the type by adopting a 'Cooperative Learning' teaching mannequin such as 'Jigsaw'. By which, students can be in mixed capability teams/base groups where they practice and boost competencies collectively cooperatively. Afterward, they can compete in opposition to individuals from different teams/base organizations of comparable abilities.[3] Whereas, with less able students, it might also be extra advisable to use a greater 'traditional' teaching mannequin where pupils' growth through a vary of trainer led activities and competencies before progressing to enjoying games. Below are a few volleyball activities, example talent cards and instructing considerations taken from the 'Full Volleyball Pack' that you can use in your lessons.

- Activity: pass and hit volleyball.

Description: development from 'throw and trap volleyball' (p.9). Pupils play 3v3 or 4v4 volleyball with modified rules. The game has to always commence with an underarm serve throw with no spin. Receiving team are allowed to catch the ball on their first touch, pass by to the setter (player close to the middle of the net), who then can pass the ball (preferably using the set omit technique) to a teammate who can hit the ball with any method they like. The opposing team tries to continue the rally the use of the identical sequence – capture – bypass – hit. Play continues until the ball hits the floor, goes out of bounds, the ball is caught out of sequence, a participant touches

the ball twice in-a-row, or extra than 3 touches have been made. Assign a factor to the group that gained the rally. Winning crew serves. [4]

Teaching Points

- Keep your eyes on the ball and be alert
- Knees bent, hips flexed, weight on the balls of feet
- Move early to the ball
- Activity: cooperative rally and rotate

Description: Students work in organizations of 6, three gamers on contrary facets of the court docket in a line. Teacher or pupil stands off the courtroom by means of the sideline post, enjoying the position of feeder. From here the feeder throws the ball underhand high and looping to the front player in the line. This participant then hits the ball over the net to the front player on the opposite facet of the court, and then moves to the returned of the equal line. Receiving participant tries to return the ball again over the internet again with one-touch. The goal of the undertaking is to preserve a rally with the gamers on the opposing aspect as lengthy as possible. When the rally comes to an end. The ball is again to the feeder, and the method begins again. This exercise works properly with two groups on a court, who can compete against every other trying to get as many hits in-a-row as possible. [5]

Teaching Points

- Hips flexed, leaning forwards aligning shoulders over your knees
- Place back of hand in the palm of the other, palms facing up
- Wrists together to create a flat platform for the ball to bounce off

Skill Cards: When instructing Volleyball it can be extraordinarily useful for college students to use ability playing cards to deepen their understanding of ability techniques. For example, when attempting to teach college students how to execute a Pass (aka Bump, Forearm Pass) they could use the above skill card to examine about the approach with a partner. Then they can take turns working towards the ability whilst their associate observes and offers feedback.

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